

Effect of Structural Factor and MWCNTs on Mechanical Response of Filament Wound CFRP Cylinders

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Abstract: The filament wound carbon fiber reinforced epoxy (CFRP) composite cylinders have been extensively used in a variety of applications due to potential advantages over conventional material made cylinders, such as high strength, modulus and specific energy absorption, etc. Effect of structural factor and amide various multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) on mechanical response of filament wound CFRP cylinder was examined in this study. It was found that CFRP tubes with end reinforcing layer exhibited higher compressive properties and such tubes sequentially showed the brittle fracturing mode, the local buckling fracturing mode and transverse shearing fracturing mode with the winding angle increasing, respectively, with the characterizations of mechanical testing, SEM and optical microscopy. The crack propagation initiated by pre-crack and subsequent failure in the cylinder was strongly dependent of pre-crack angle due to deflection and penetration competition of crack evolution. Moreover, the addition of various MWCNTs barely affected mechanical properties of CFRP cylinders and epoxy matrix except the compressive modulus. Specifically, MWCNTs-NH₂ endowed highest enhancement on compressive modulus of the cylinders by 63.7% due to their uniform dispersion and excellent interfacial adhesion compared to MWCNTs-COOH and raw MWCNTs. Raman characterization revealed that all layers of MWCNTs contributed and showed their whole performance under compression, while only the outer nanotube layers played a role through interfacial friction with resin matrix under tension, which resulted in more significant enhancement of compressive modulus with respect to tensile modulus. Additionally, specific energy absorption of CFRP cylinders was also enhanced by MWCNTs as a result of their effect on micro-crack initiation. Acoustic emission (AE) detection illustrated that MWCNTs created a positive effect to effectively trigger abundant micro-cracks to prevent macro-crack formation and subsequently delay cylinder collapse with ultrahigh AE energy appearing.

Keywords: MWCNTs; cylinder; damage mechanics; crack; acoustic emission

1. Introduction

The filament winding process was an efficient technique, commonly used in the mass production of high performance CFRP tubes. The properties and performance of the filament wound products like tubes were mainly affected by geometric and winding factors such as end reinforcing layer and winding angle etc [1-2]. The practical applications of CFRP tubes required adequate assessment of their response under severe conditions like high compression loading. Specifically, crushing failure was of much interest, which often limited engineering applications of CFRP tubes due to the lower compressive strength relative to tensile strength. At present, however, there was a large uncertainty of understanding **crushing characteristics of filament wound carbon fiber/epoxy tube**. To this end, effect of structural factor and amide grafted multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWNT_S-NH₂) on crushing characteristics of filament wound CFRP tube under quasi-static compression condition was examined with the characterizations of mechanical testing, SEM and optical microscopy, etc.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Sample preparation

Diglycidyl ester of aliphatic cyclo (DGEAC) type epoxy resin (epoxy value, 0.85), DDM, DETDA, 2,4-EMI and T700 carbon fibers (CFs) were used in this study. Amide grafted multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWNT_S-NH₂) were prepared using the procedure in our previous works [3]. The epoxy resin system was obtained by uniformly mixing MWNT_S-NH₂, DGEAC resin, DDM, DETDA and 2,4-EMI. Filament wound CFRP tubes with various winding angles were prepared with the filament winding machine

2.2. Characterizations

The axial compression tests of specimen tubes were performed between two flat platens on a testing machine (Instron 1121) to obtain the compressive strengths, compressive modulus and stroke efficiency. Morphologies of fractured surfaces of CFRP tubes were observed by scanning electron microscopy (S4700, HITACHI Co., Tokyo, Japan). The failure mode of CFRP tube was predicted with Material type 54 in LS-DYNA, using the Chang-Chang failure criterion [4-5].

3. Results and discussion

Fig. 1. Effect of winding angle on compressive strength and modulus of CFRP tubes

Fig.1 shows the effect of winding angle on the compressive strength and modulus of CFRP tubes. With winding angle increasing, the compressive strength generally exhibited the decreasing trend as showed in Fig.1, while the strength value was minimum at the winding angle of 40°, which agreed with similar studies on glass fiber reinforced pipes by other researchers [6-7]. The decreasing trend was obviously attributed to the reduction of load bearing by the fiber and the resultant enhancement of longitudinal deformation because of the decreasing of fiber alignment along the longitudinal axis with winding angle increasing. However, the minimum value of compressive strength was related with the local buckling crushing mode of the tube with the winding angle of 40°. Furthermore, the compressive modulus of the tubes linearly decreased with the winding angles as showed in Fig.1.

Fig.2 shows optical images of fractured CFRP tubes with various winding angles. It could be seen that the macro-cracks propagated just along the direction of winding angles for 20°, 60° and 80°, implying that the cracks perpendicular to the fiber direction were inhibited effectively by the fibers. However, for the tube with winding angle of 40°, the failure occurred along with the plastic deformation in the central circumference and no fractured fibers were observed. Thus, the morphologies of fracturing cracks of these tubes were quite different, which was strongly related with the crushing mechanisms at different winding angles.

Fig.3 shows SEM images of fractured surfaces of CFRP tubes with various winding angles. At the winding angle of 20° , the fractured surfaces were scalloped and a large number of interlaminar and longitudinal cracks were found as showed in Fig.2(a) and Fig.3(a), which were the characteristics of brittle fracturing mode [8]. At the higher angles of 60° and 80° , the wedge-shaped cross-section of the laminate with interlaminar and longitudinal cracks were clearly observed from Fig.3(c) and (d), which manifested the typical feature of transverse shearing crushing mode [9]. However, the crushing behavior was much different at the winding angle of 40° compared to other angles. As showed in Fig.2(b), the deformation of the material between adjacent buckle nodes showed elastic characteristics, while the plastic deformation of the material at a buckle node was not uniformly distributed through the thickness of the tube. All these features implied that the crushing behavior of the tube with winding angle of 40° was predominated by the local buckling crushing mode.

Fig. 2. Optical images of fractured CFRP tubes with winding angles of (a) 20° , (b) 40° , (c) 60° and (d) 80° . Images of (a1), (b1), (c1) and (d1) show the corresponding high-resolution optical images of the cracks, respectively.

Fig. 3. SEM images of fractured surfaces of CFRP tubes with winding angles of (a) 20°, (b) 40°, (c) 60° and (d) 80°.

Fig. 4. Effect of pre-crack angle on compressive strength and modulus of CFRP tubes.

Fig.4 shows the effect of pre-crack angle on compressive strength and modulus of CFRP tubes. With the pre-crack angle increasing, the compressive strength and modulus initially decreased to the minimum values when the pre-crack angle equaled or close to the winding angle, and subsequently increased. This variation trend was attributed to the decrease and increase of depression effect of the fibers on the crack propagation in the tube with the included angle variation between pre-crack angle and winding angle. Specifically, the cracks initiated from the pre-crack propagated more easily in the condition of the pre-crack angle parallel to the winding angle.

Fig.5 Experimental failure images and simulated compression strain distribution of CFRP tube with pre-crack angles of (a) 0, (b) 60 and (f) 90.

Fig.5 shows experimental failure images and simulated compression strain distribution of CFRP tubes with various pre-crack angles. As showed in simulated compression strain distribution in Fig.5, the tubes would be damaged from the location with maximum compression strain. Noticeably, the simulated failure model generally conformed to experimental crushing behaviors for CFRP tubes with various pre-crack angles, which proved that the Chang-Chang failure criteria could accurately represent the quasi-static crushing failure of laminates in the tube. However, the crushing behavior of the tubes with various pre-crack angles was quite

different. The crack propagation initiated by pre-crack and the fracture region formed at the interface in the tube were strongly dependent of pre-crack angle as a result of the competition between deflection effect and penetration effect of crack evolution.

Fig.6. FT-IR spectra of (a) commercial MWNTs, (b) MWNT_S-COOH and (c) MWNT_S-NH₂)

Fig. 6. shows the FTIR spectra of commercial MWNTs, MWNT_S-COOH and MWNT_S-NH₂. In fig.5 (b), the absorption peaks at 1701 and 3430.4 cm⁻¹ were attributed to the carboxylic C=O and O–H stretching vibration, which manifested that the carboxylic acid groups were attached to the nanotubes successfully after acid treatment. In Fig.6 (c), the peak for the N–H stretching vibrations of amine groups appeared at 3421cm⁻¹. The result demonstrated that the amine functionalization of MWNTs was carried out successfully.

Table 1 **Effect** of MWNT_S-NH₂ on compressive properties of the tube.

MWNT _S -NH ₂ Loading (wt.%)	compressive strength (MPa)	compressive modulus (GPa)	Strain (%)
0	143±3	4.7±0.2	3.4±0.3
0.5	141±2	7.9±0.3	1.7±0.2

Table 1 shows **effect** of MWNT-NH₂ on compressive properties the tube. By the addition of 0.5 wt.% MWNT_S-NH₂, the compressive strength of the tube remained almost constant, while the compressive modulus of the tube was significantly improved by 68.4 % so that the strain-to-failure was accordingly declined by 44 %. Based on the uniform dispersion and strong interaction of MWNT-NH₂ with matrix and fibers, this observed improvement was due to the high modulus (at least 400 Gpa) of MWNTs, which was far beyond the modulus value (~240 GPa) of T700 carbon fiber.

4. Conclusions

With winding angle increasing, the tubes showed the brittle fracturing mode, local buckling crushing mode and transverse shearing crushing mode, respectively, along with the general decreasing of the compressive strength and modulus. Besides, with pre-crack angle increasing, the compressive strength and modulus of the tube initially decreased to the minimum values when the pre-crack angle equaled or close to the winding angle, and subsequently increased. The crack propagation initiated by pre-crack and the fracture region formed at the interface in the tube were strongly dependent of pre-crack angle due to the competition between deflection effect and penetration effect of crack evolution. Moreover, the simulated failure mode correlated well with the experimental results as well as the compressive modulus of the tube was significantly improved by the addition of MWNT_S-NH₂.

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References

- [1] Morozov EV. The effect of filament winding mosaic patterns on the strength of thin-walled composite shells. *Compos Struct* 2006; 76(1/2): 123-9.
- [2] Rousseau J, Perreux D, Verdietre N. The influence of winding patterns on the damage behaviour of filament-wound pipes. *Compos Sci Technol* 1999; 59(9): 1439-49.
- [3] Li XC, Sui G, Yang XP, Yu YH, Shi LF. The Improvement of wettability, mechanical and thermo-mechanical performances of PBO fiber/epoxy composites by adding reactive carbon nanotubes. *Polym Polym Compos* 2011; 19(4-5): 391-6.

- [4] Chang FK, Chang KY. Post-failure analysis of bolted composite joints in tension or shear-out mode failure. *J Compos Mater* 1987; 21: 809-33.
- [5] Labeas G, Belesis S, Stamatelos D. Interaction of damage failure and post-buckling behaviour of composite plates with cut-outs by progressive damage modeling. *Compos Part B* 2008; 39: 304-15.
- [6] Moon CJ, Kim IH, Choi BH, Kweon JH, Choi JH. Buckling of filament-wound composite tubes subjected to hydrostatic pressure for underwater vehicle applications. *Compos Struct* 2010; 92: 2241-51.
- [7] Liu HK, Liao WC, Tseng L, Lee WH, Sawada Y. Compression strength of pre-damaged concrete tubes reinforced by non-adhesive filament wound composites. *Compos Part A* 2004; 35: 281-92.
- [8] Farley GL, Jones RM. Crushing characteristics of continuous fiber-reinforced composite tubes. *J Compos Mater* 1992; 26(1): 37-50.
- [9] Mamalis AG, Manolakas DE. Crashworthy behavior of thin-walled tubes of fiberglass composite materials subjected to axial loading. *J Compos Mater* 1990; 24: 72-91.